

Pre-Deflection Routing with Control Packet Signal Scheme in Optical Burst Switch Networks

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Abstract : Optical Burst Switching (OBS) is a promising technology for the future generation Internet. Control architecture and Contention resolution are the main issues faced by the Optical Burst Switching networks. In this paper we are only taking care of the Contention problem and to overcome this issue we propose Pre-Deflection Routing with Control Packet Signal Scheme for Contention Resolution in Optical Burst Switch Networks. In this paper Pre-deflection routing approach has been proposed in which routing is carried out in two ways, Shortest Path First (SPF) and Least Hop First (LHF) Routing to forward the clusters and canoes respectively. Hereafter Burst Offset Time Control Algorithm has been proposed where a forward control packet (FCP) collects the congestion price and contention price along its paths. Thereafter a reverse-direction control packet (RCP) sent by destination node which delivers the information of FCP to the source node, and source node uses this information to revise its offset time and burst length.

Keywords : Contention Resolution, FCP, OBS, Offset Time, PST, RCP.

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